

Interaction of Sulphur Monochloride with Organic Acid Amides.

Part II

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It is well-known that dry gaseous ammonia interacts vigorously with sulphur monochloride with the precipitation of sulphur (Naik, T., 1921, 119, 1166). In a previous communication (*loc. cit.*), it was shown that when this ammoniacal reactivity was neutralised by strong acid residues, *e.g.*, in the organic acid amides such as oxamide, malonamide, succinamide, phthalamide, etc., sulphur monochloride reacts no longer. Between these two extreme limits, of vigorous reactivity and no reactivity, come a number of cases where the reactivity of the amido group is only partially neutralised by the acid character of other residue.

The amides of acetic and benzoic acids interact with sulphur monochloride giving a mono-sulphide (*loc. cit.*), which is presumably derived from a disulphide, $\left. \begin{array}{l} -\text{NH} \\ -\text{NH} \end{array} \right\} \text{S}=\text{S}$, that had been initially formed.

The work described in this paper was undertaken with a view to throw some additional light on the conditions governing the reactivity of the amido group in organic

acid amides, and also on those which govern the stability of the sulphur atom present in the resulting monosulphides. By weakening the acid residue of the amides still further, the reactivity of the amido group may be slowly increased, a point being ultimately reached where it is possible that the monosulphide would change into a condensed di-imido

or hydrazine, $\left. \begin{array}{c} -\text{NH} \\ | \\ -\text{NH} \end{array} \right\}$ derivative, a limit, which, if achieved, would correspond to a stage just below the extreme one, *viz.*, when dry ammonia interacts with sulphur monochloride.

With the above end in view, isobutyramide, valeramide, and capronamide were selected. The reaction with sulphur monochloride in all the three cases followed a very simple course, two molecules of the amide condensing to give a di-amide with profuse evolution of hydrogen chloride and the total elimination of all the sulphur, thus :

and so on for the others.

These products which showed no trace of sulphur usually had showed higher melting points than the original amides from which they were found to be different by the method of mixed melting points. The molecular weights, too, when determined by the cryoscopic method, gave results in complete accord with those required for the condensed product. Moreover, the di-imido product obtained from capronamide, gave the original amide, on reduction with alcoholic sodium hydrosulphide, thus proving its constitution.

The effect of strengthening the acid group on the reactivity of the amido group, was also studied by selecting monochloroacetamide and trichloroacetamide as typical examples. Whereas the ammoniacal reactivity of the amido group in acetamide and monochloroacetamide was sufficient to give a monosulphide, that in trichloroacetamide was reduced to the desired extent and gave the expected di-imido product, thus :

Experiments were also instituted with a view to examine the possibilities of transferring the activity from the amido group in CH_3CONH_2 to the methylene group by substituting one of the hydrogen atoms of the methyl group by acidic groups such as phenyl and cyanogen (*cf.* Naik, T., 1921, 119, 379). The reaction with phenylacetamide was inconclusive, and is being investigated more thoroughly, whilst in the case of cyanacetamide the reactivity was found to be transferred from the amido to the methylene group, thus :

The reaction was very vigorous, as was the case with cyanacetic ester (Naik, T., 1921, 119, 1232).

Further, the reactions of sulphur monochloride with substituted amides such as isobutyranilide, phenylacetanilide, and acetyl salicylanilide were studied. Whereas isobutyranilide and phenylacetanilide gave a disulphide, thus resembling the reaction of salicylamide, (*loc. cit.*):

acetylsalicylanilide gave a trisulphide, resembling the reactions of acetanilide and benzanilide with sulphur monochloride:

On nitration of the disulphide resulting from (VI), a tetranitroderivative was obtained as before (*loc. cit.*).

EXPERIMENTAL

Symm-dicaproyl hydrazine.

Capronamide (3 grams) and sulphur monochloride (2 grams) were separately dissolved in dry petroleum (25 c.c. for each) and boiled under a reflux condenser. The reaction started with evolution of hydrogen chloride.

After three hours the flask was allowed to cool and a viscous mass deposited at the bottom. The excess of sulphur monochloride was washed away with dry petroleum and the product was kept overnight in vacuum in an alkali desiccator. On being boiled with animal charcoal in benzene and filtered, it deposited from the clear filtrate on cooling, in plates with pearly lustre, and melted on recrystallisation at 111—112°C. The original amide melted at 98°C, while the mixture of the two melted at 95°C. It was easily soluble in benzene, alcohol, acetone and warm water, more difficultly soluble in chloroform, insoluble in petroleum and carbon disulphide.

Molecular Complexity.—A specimen recrystallised from benzene and carefully dried gave the following molecular complexity by the cryoscopic method in this solvent; 0·0102 grams and 0·0152 grams dissolved in 20 c.c. of benzene depressed the freezing point by 0·011°C and 0·019°C, respectively; $M=265$, 229 (average 247). $C_{12}H_{24}O_2N_2$ requires $M=228$. (Found : $N=12\cdot39$. $C_{12}H_{24}O_2N_2$ requires $N=12\cdot28$ per cent.). There was no sulphur in the compound.

Reduction.—5 grams of the above compound were dissolved in 50 c.c. of absolute alcohol and an aqueous solution of sodium hydrosulphide and caustic soda was gradually added (Brand, Ber., 1906, 42, 3464). On cooling a crystalline precipitate was obtained. The crystals were washed free from alkali with hot water and the product on recrystallisation from alcohol melted at 98°C. It was found to be pure capronamide.

Symm-divaleryl hydrazine.

Valeramide (3 grams) and sulphur monochloride (2·5 grams) were separately dissolved in dry petroleum (15 c.c. in each case), mixed and boiled. Hydrogen chloride began to evolve on heating this mixture. The brown viscous

solid deposited on completion of reaction (3 hours), gave shining pearly plates from benzene, as in the case of capronamide, which melted at 123°C. It was soluble in benzene, alcohol, acetone and also in warm water, but insoluble in petroleum and carbon bisulphide.

Molecular Complexity.—0.0194 gram of the substance dissolved in 20 c.c. of benzene depressed the freezing point by 0.025°C; $M=222$. $C_{10}H_{20}N_2O_2$ requires $M=200$. (Found: $N=14.25$. $C_{10}H_{20}O_2N_2$ requires $N=14.00$ per cent.). Sulphur was found to be absent.

Symm-di-isobutyryl hydrazine.

Isobutyramide (3 grams) and sulphur monochloride (3 grams) dissolved in dry petroleum (50 c.c.) were boiled under a reflux condenser. Copious evolution of hydrogen chloride was observed. After treatment of the brown viscous residue in the same way as before, pearly white plates melting at 120—121°C were obtained. The product was found to be easily soluble in benzene, alcohol and acetone, but only slightly soluble in chloroform.

Molecular Complexity.—0.0088 grams of the substance dissolved in 20 c.c. of benzene depressed the freezing point by 0.014°C. $M=180$. $C_8H_{16}O_2N_2$ requires $M=172$. (Found: $N=16.20$. $C_8H_{16}O_2N_2$ requires $N=16.28$ per cent.). The compound contained no sulphur.

N-sulphidolies-chloracetamide.

A mixture of monochloracetamide (3 grams) and sulphur monochloride (3 grams) in 50 c.c. of dry benzene was boiled till the evolution of hydrogen chloride ceased. A white solid was gradually deposited. The reaction was stopped after 6 hours, the product filtered, washed free from sulphur monochloride and crystallised from hot alcohol, when it was obtained in shining white crystals. It begins to melt at 165°C (decomp.), forming a yellow liquid.

(Found : N = 13.14 ; S = 14.5 ; Cl = 32.26. $C_4H_5O_2N_2Cl_2S$ requires N = 12.90 ; S = 14.75 and Cl = 32.72 per cent.).

Symm-hexachlordiacetyl hydrazine.

Trichloracetamide (6 grams) and sulphur monochloride (2 grams) were boiled in dry benzene (50 c.c.) as in the previous case. A brisk evolution of hydrogen chloride was noted. On cooling a yellowish white mass was deposited which on being freed from the excess of sulphur monochloride and sulphur, was crystallised from benzene and obtained in the form of white needles. On recrystallisation from benzene it melted at 148—149°C. Trichloracetamide melts at 140°C.

Molecular Complexity.—0.0423 grams of the substance dissolved in 20 c.c. of benzene depressed the freezing point by 0.035°C. $M = 338$. $C_4H_5O_2N_2Cl_2S$ requires $M = 323$. (Found : N = 8.80 ; Cl = 65.80. $C_4H_5O_2N_2Cl_2S$ requires N = 8.67 and Cl = 65.94 per cent.). No sulphur was detected in this compound.

Cyanacetamide-C-disulphide.

Cyanacetamide (3 grams) and sulphur monochloride (3 grams) were boiled in dry benzene (50 c.c.). A brown granular mass was obtained as the evolution of hydrogen chloride proceeded quickly. On completion of the reaction (after 4 hours), the excess of sulphur monochloride was removed by hot benzene. The product was freed from sulphur by being repeatedly boiled under a reflux condenser with carbon disulphide until the melting point became constant. It melts at 103°C (decomp.) ; it is insoluble in benzene, petroleum and carbon disulphide, and hydrolyses in alcohol. On standing it undergoes slow decomposition to a dark mass. (Found : N = 24.77 ; S = 27.73. $C_2H_3O_2N_4S_2$ requires N = 24.34 and S = 27.82 per cent.).

Symm-di-isobutyryl-diamino-diphenyl disulphide.

Isobutyranilide (3 grams) and sulphur monochloride

(3 grams) were boiled together in dry benzene (50 c.c.) for 12 hours. The resulting pink coloured solution was slowly evaporated in a current of dry hot air, when an indigo coloured mass was obtained. On boiling in benzene with animal charcoal and leaving the solid mass obtained on evaporation of the solvent benzene, in an alkaline desiccator, it was freed from the hydrogen chloride with which it was at first contaminated. The resulting granular mass was redissolved in benzene from which it was deposited in the form of an indigo coloured amorphous granular powder melting at 100—102°C (decomp.), very easily soluble in benzene forming a beautiful violet coloured solution and also soluble in alcohol and acetone. (Found : N=7.55 ; S=16.9. $C_{20}H_{24}O_2N_2S_2$ requires N=7.22 and S=16.5 per cent.).

Symm-diphenyl-diacetyl-diamino-diphenyl-disulphide.

Equal quantities (5 grams) of phenylacetanilide and sulphur monochloride were boiled together in dry benzene (50 c.c.) for 15 hours. The excess of sulphur monochloride was then evaporated in a draught of dry air, the viscous solid residue redissolved in benzene and precipitated by petroleum. It melted at 162 to 163°C. (Found : N=5.68, S=12.98. $C_{28}H_{24}O_2N_2S_2$ requires N=5.79 and S=13.22 per cent.).

Symm-tetranitro-diphenyl-diacetyl-diamino-diphenyl-disulphide.

Two grams of the above substance were gradually treated with 10 c.c. fuming nitric acid (S. G. 1.5), keeping the temperature low. At first a sudden evolution of the oxides of nitrogen took place, the disulphide going into solution at the same time. The liquid was slightly concentrated, allowed to cool and filtered, when on slight dilution with water, a very pure yellowish mass was

obtained, which melted at 148—150°C (decomp.). (Found : N=12·76 ; S=9·23. $C_{22}H_{20}O_{10}N_6S_2$ requires N=12·65 and S=9·64 per cent.).

Symm-diacetoxy-dianilino-diformyl-diphenyl-trisulphide.

Acetylsalicylanilide (4 grams) were boiled in dry benzene (100 c.c.) with sulphur monochloride (3 grams) for eighteen hours. After the evaporation of the solution in a current of dry air, the dirty white viscous mass obtained was redissolved in benzene and boiled with animal charcoal. The clear filtrate was allowed to drop into a large quantity of petroleum ether, when a partly granular and partly viscous mass was obtained. This was left in an alkaline desiccator overnight, dissolved in benzene and precipitated by petroleum in the form of a light yellow powder which melted at 78°C (decomp.). (Found : S=15·62. $C_{30}H_{24}O_6N_2S_3$ requires S=15·89 per cent.).

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